

Citizen Science is a sticky business according to CS Track preliminary survey findings

A new white paper entitled **Themes, objectives and participants of citizen science activities** has just been released by the CS Track project. This brief summary of the main characteristics of the themes and objectives of citizen science projects and the people who participate will inform the development of policy recommendations and best practice manuals.

This white paper, along with the first results of the large scale survey into Citizen Science carried out by project partner JYU shows that Citizen Science activities have been boosted by the widespread availability of smartphones and related technologies. Preliminary research findings also suggest that around 4 in 5 people who take part in citizen science projects, tend to stick with them until the end and more than a third of the respondents have been taking part in citizen science projects for more than 10 years.

The white paper also shows that Citizen Science project themes tend to focus on agricultural, biological and environmental sciences while emerging themes include applied sciences like engineering, medicine, and government policy-related fields. Citizen Science projects generally address multiple and overlapping goals that vary from monitoring and research to education, public outreach, social justice and societal change. In terms of participation, this work confirms that Citizen Science projects tend to attract well-educated, affluent participants with male citizen scientists generally outnumbering female citizen scientists.

Download the full report available [here](#).

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